

Integrated utilisation of LH₂ boil-off gas in liquid air energy storage: a 3E techno-economic assessment

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Abstract

Liquid hydrogen (LH₂) import and export terminals typically experience continuous boil-off gas (BOG) generation of 0.05–1% of throughput, resulting in a significant loss of the high-grade cryogenic exergy invested in hydrogen liquefaction. While various BOG management strategies exist, the opportunity to convert this waste cold into a storable, flexible energy asset remains underexplored. This paper investigates the integration of liquid air energy storage (LAES) with LH₂ terminals through direct thermal energy transfer from hydrogen BOG to ambient air, enabling air liquefaction and storage as liquid air for later power generation. A comprehensive 3E assessment, covering energy, exergy and economic performance, is conducted. The novelty of this work lies in coupling LH₂ BOG management with LAES to transform unavoidable cryogenic losses into a multi-service energy resource, applying a unified 3E framework to enable comparison with alternative integration strategies, and identifying design and operating windows that maximise both exergy recovery and economic value. The proposed framework therefore provides design guidelines for next-generation LH₂ terminals with embedded cold-energy recovery and utilisation.

Keywords

Liquid hydrogen, Boil-off gas, Liquid air energy storage, Cryogenic energy storage, 3E analysis

1 Introduction

Hydrogen is attracting increasing attention as a strategic future low-carbon energy systems. This interest is supported by the expected expansion of the global hydrogen market, with worldwide hydrogen demand reaching approximately 94.3 Mt H₂ in 2021 and projected to increase to around 179.9 Mt H₂ by 2030 under the International Energy Agency Net Zero Emissions scenario [1]. This anticipated expansion reflects the growing role of hydrogen in decarbonising sectors where direct electrification remains challenging. Within this context, liquid hydrogen (LH₂) is particularly relevant for decentralised hydrogen infrastructure and wider distribution networks, where compact storage and improved transportability are increasingly important.

Storing hydrogen as a cryogenic liquid at 20.28 K and 1.013 bar increases its volumetric density to 70.953 kg/m³, which is substantially

higher than that of compressed gaseous hydrogen at 500 bar, approximately 31.218 kg/m³. These values illustrate why hydrogen liquefaction is often required when high storage density is needed. However, although liquefaction improves storage compactness, LH₂ storage, transfer, and handling are associated with unavoidable cryogenic losses that lead to boil-off gas (BOG) formation. Hydrogen BOG represents not only a direct loss of stored hydrogen and the related chemical exergy of the released hydrogen, but also a loss of the cryogenic exergy previously invested in liquefaction. At present, BOG loss mitigation relies mainly on insulation, which has practical limitations and additional capital cost.

Morgan et al. [2] presented an internally recuperated LAES configuration in which the cold thermal energy released during the discharge process is captured in a cold thermal store and later reused during charging to reduce the air-liquefaction work. For a reference 20 MW/80 MWh LAES plant, they reported that recovering approximately 300 kJ/kg of liquid air, equivalent to 93% of the available cold, enabled the round-trip efficiency to exceed 50%, with the optimised cycle reaching 47–57% depending on the grade of warm recycle. The study investigated a conventional LAES cold-recovery approach, in which the recovered cold originates from the system's own discharge section rather than being treated as independent from the discharge.

In the context of external cryogenic streams to enhance LAES performance and reduce losses during hydrogen terminal operation Kim et al. [3] proposed an integrated LH₂ regasification and LAES process, in which the cold energy released during LH₂ regasification is used to support air liquefaction, while the stored liquid air is later expanded for power generation. They analysed three configurations, including a compressor-assisted case, a compressor-free case using LH₂ cold energy directly, and a configuration combined with an organic Rankine cycle (ORC) for additional cold-energy recovery. The highest-performing case achieved a round-trip efficiency of 150.2% and an exergy efficiency of 59.7%, while the economic analysis reported a positive net present value, corresponding to 38.61 USD per tonne of annual LH₂ capacity for their 1 MTPA regasification plant. This work therefore demonstrates the potential of using LH₂ regasification cold energy as an external cryogenic source for LAES charging and power recovery, rather than relying only on internally recovered cold from the LAES discharge process.

The present study proposes the integration of LH₂ BOG cold recovery with a LAES system, demonstrated here at small scale for a representative case study. The concept scales directly with LH₂ storage inventory, and the performance is expected to improve at larger scale, since the isentropic efficiencies of the rotating equipment increase considerably with machine size. The novelty of this study lies in coupling LH₂ BOG management with LAES within a unified energy, exergy and economic framework, enabling the simultaneous assessment of liquefaction performance, exergy recovery and system value. This approach utilises the cold content of LH₂ BOG as a useful cryogenic resource, while delivering the warmed hydrogen stream under suitable conditions for subsequent chemical-exergy utilisation. By quantifying both the cold-energy contribution to air liquefaction and the economic value of the recovered hydrogen stream, this work demonstrates how unavoidable BOG generation can be converted from a storage penalty into a useful energy and material resource for future LH₂ storage and distribution infrastructure.

2 Process description

2.1 Charging section

Fig. 1 illustrates the overall layout of the proposed LAES configuration integrated with LH₂ BOG cold recovery. The proposed system was modelled in Aspen HYSYS, with thermodynamic property calculations performed using the REFPROP INST dataset. The compression configuration of the developed system was selected via a parametric study in MATLAB, based on the A7_out stream temperature and the input power. Atmospheric air is compressed through a four-stage intercooled compression train (C1-4) reaching 7470 kPa. The high-pressure air stream is then divided into two branches with a split ratio of 10:1. The smaller branch, stream A6, is routed through HEX100 for pre-cooling before entering the expander, K-101, while the main branch, stream A7, passes directly through the cold box, HEX101. The cold box receives three cold streams: the

expanded A6 stream, the direct BOG flow from the LH₂ reservoir, and the vapour generated from the liquid air buffer tank. The BOG stream enters the cold box at ambient pressure and 22 K. For the present case study, based on a 1000 m³ LH₂ reservoir, the BOG mass flow rate is approximately 3.6 kg/h. The return vapour from the liquid air buffer tank enters the cold box at 5470 kPa and 110.3 K. The main compressed air stream, A7, is fully liquefied in the cold box and exits at 110 K.

The process is designed with a throttling valve (VLV-100) before the liquid-air reservoir because the cold-box outlet stream is still at a high pressure of 7470 kPa. The valve reduces the stream pressure to the storage pressure of 5470 kPa and brings the liquid air to the appropriate thermodynamic condition for storage. During this pressure reduction, part of the liquid may flash into vapour, especially if the stream is not sufficiently subcooled. In this configuration, however, this vapour is not treated as a direct loss; instead, it is returned to the cold box through the Air_return stream, where its remaining cryogenic exergy is recovered to assist in cooling and liquefying the incoming compressed air.

After recovering the cold exergy in the cold box, the BOG stream will be ready to be delivered to the other plant for chemical-exergy utilisation at a temperature of 282 K and 101.3 kPa. This design avoids the considerably higher boil-off formation associated with low-pressure liquid-air storage and also reduces the required pressure lift during cryogenic pumping in the discharge stage. As a result, the selected configuration provides a practical trade-off between reduced boil-off generation, lower pumping demand, cold-exergy recovery and overall cycle efficiency, although it requires the reservoir to be designed as a pressurised cryogenic storage vessel.

2.2 Discharging section

In the discharging section, liquid air at 5470 kPa and 110.3 K from the pressurised liquid air buffer tank is pumped to the seawater heater at a pressure of 10 MPa and a temperature of 114.6 K. The air flow is then delivered to a three-stage expansion train with interheating, generating 2.3 kW of power. Due to the relatively small scale of the

Figure 1: Process flow diagram of the proposed LH₂ BOG-assisted LAES system.

process, the isentropic efficiencies of the expanders and compressors are considered to be relatively low, with a value of 75%. In the proposed process design, the liquefaction process does not rely on cold energy recovered from the discharge stage as a required precooling source, which is commonly used in many conventional LAES configurations. This provides an operational advantage, as the charging section can be operated independently of the discharge section. Consequently, the system can be treated as a stand-alone liquefaction process, while the discharge stage can be reserved mainly for peak-demand periods rather than being operated continuously for cold-energy recovery.

3 Energy and exergy analysis

The performance of the proposed LH₂ BOG-assisted LAES configuration was evaluated through energy and exergy analyses to quantify the air-liquefaction performance, power consumption, power recovery and utilisation of the cryogenic exergy carried by the BOG stream. Particular attention is given to the cold box, where the BOG stream, expanded air stream and return vapour from the liquid air buffer tank jointly contribute to the cooling and liquefaction of the compressed air. This assessment provides the basis for evaluating the

effectiveness of LH₂ BOG cold recovery in improving the liquefaction performance and overall thermodynamic behaviour of the proposed small-scale LAES system. The integrated system achieves a high liquefaction fraction of 90%, which is well above the performance typically expected from a stand-alone Linde-Hampson process. This improvement is mainly due to the recovery of cold exergy from the LH₂ BOG stream, which improves the thermal matching between the hot and cold composite curves in HEX101, as presented in Fig. 2. A minimum temperature approach of approximately 5 K is maintained throughout the heat-exchange process within the cold box.

The corresponding specific energy consumption (SEC) of the charging process is 0.23 kWh/kg_{LAir}. Based on the definition presented in Equation (1), the figure of merit (FOM) is calculated as the ratio of the minimum reversible work of liquefaction, represented by the liquid-air exergy output, to the actual charging work input:

$$FOM = \frac{W_{min}}{SEC} = \frac{\dot{E}_{x,LAir}}{\dot{W}_{charging}} \quad (1)$$

Therefore, the calculated FOM indicates that the useful exergy stored in the produced liquid air corresponds to 77.2% of the charging input considered in this analysis.

The exergy destruction in each component was evaluated from a steady-state exergy balance, neglecting kinetic and potential terms, so that the destruction equals the difference between the exergy entering and leaving the unit, with the shaft work added for the

Figure 2: Composite curve of the cold box (HEX101) in the proposed LH₂ BOG-assisted LAES system.

Table 1. Component exergy-destruction equations used in this study

equipment	Exergy destruction equation
Compressors (C1–C4)	$\dot{E}_{D,C} = \dot{W}_C + (\dot{m}e)_{in} - (\dot{m}e)_{out}$
Cryogenic pump (P-100)	$\dot{E}_{D,P} = \dot{W}_P + (\dot{m}e)_{in} - (\dot{m}e)_{out}$
Expanders (K-101 to K-104)	$\dot{E}_{D,EX} = (\dot{m}e)_{in} - (\dot{m}e)_{out} - \dot{W}_{EX}$
Cold box / multi-stream HEX (HEX101)	$\dot{E}_{D,HEX101} = \sum_{in} (\dot{m}e) - \sum_{out} (\dot{m}e)$
Two-stream HEX (HEX100)	$\dot{E}_{D,HEX100} = \sum_i \dot{m}_i (e_{in} - e_{out})_i$
Intercoolers / seawater heaters	$\dot{E}_{D,HX} = \sum_{in} (\dot{m}e) - \sum_{out} (\dot{m}e)$
Throttle valve (VLV-100)	$\dot{E}_{D,VLV} = (\dot{m}e)_{in} - (\dot{m}e)_{out}$

Figure 3: Exergy flow diagram of the proposed process during charging and discharging

compressors and pump and subtracted for the expanders. The specific physical exergy of each stream is defined from its enthalpy and entropy relative to the dead state. The resulting component-level expressions are summarised in Table 1. Each balance can be expressed equivalently as the product of the dead-state temperature and the entropy generation rate, so the dead-state temperature enters every term directly; this is clearest for the throttling valve, which is isenthalpic and therefore destroys exergy in proportion to the dead-state temperature and the entropy rise across it. These expressions were applied to obtain the component exergy-destruction values reported in the exergy-flow diagram (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3 represents the exergy flow through both sections of the proposed process, namely the charging section and the discharging section, and highlights the main exergy inputs, useful outputs and destruction/loss terms across the system.

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As depicted in the exergy-flow diagram (Figure 3), the LH₂ boil-off gas supplies 5.6 kW of exergy to the storage section, but this quantity is not transferred fully and reversibly to the air side. Instead, the cold box acts as the coupling unit between the hydrogen and air streams, where the BOG exergy is split into a useful exergy transfer to the air side of about 2.4 kW and an exergy destruction of about 3.2 kW. The cryogenic air stream entering storage therefore does not arise from hydrogen cold alone; it is formed by the combination of the useful exergy transferred through the cold box and the net compressor work input of 7.9 kW, after accounting for the irreversibilities associated with air compression, intercooling and throttling. In this sense, the exergy-flow diagram shows that the BOG provides a valuable low-temperature exergy source that reduces the burden on the liquefaction stage.

The main irreversibility sources in the present configuration are concentrated in the cold box (3.2 kW) and in the discharge-side heaters and expanders (4.01 kW), while smaller but non-negligible losses occur in the air compressors and intercoolers (2.9 kW), the expansion valve (0.1 kW), the cryogenic pump (0.06 kW), and the final air discharge to the environment (0.15 kW). The exergy analysis suggests that further improvement should focus primarily on reducing cold-box irreversibility and enhancing the performance of the discharge train, since these two sections govern most of the exergy destruction in the integrated LH₂-assisted LAES process.

4 Equipment cost and economic analysis

4.1 Equipment cost

The economic evaluation of the proposed system was carried out using equipment purchase-cost correlations adapted from Kim et al. [3]. In this approach, the purchase cost of each expander was estimated from its power output using Equation (2), while the compressor and pump purchase costs were determined from their respective power requirements using Equations (3) and (4). For thermal equipment, the purchase cost of a conventional heat

exchanger was evaluated from the ratio of heat duty to logarithmic mean temperature difference, as given in Equation (5), whereas the corresponding cost of the multi-stream heat exchanger was calculated using Equation (6), which includes an additional factor to reflect the greater design and fabrication complexity of multi-stream cryogenic exchangers. The purchase cost of coolers and heaters was then estimated using Equation (7), which relates the thermal duty and logarithmic mean temperature difference to the equipment cost coefficient. In all cases, these correlations were used to estimate the individual purchase costs of the major process units prior to applying the cost-index correction and bare-module factors in the subsequent capital-cost evaluation. To allow comparison independent of plant size, the resulting equipment costs are normalised per cubic metre of LH₂ storage capacity, based on the 1000 m³ reservoir adopted in this study, as shown in Figure 4.

$$C_{\text{Exp}}^E = 0.378(1.3405\dot{W}_{\text{Exp}})^{0.81} \quad (2)$$

$$C_{\text{Comp}}^E = 7.90(1.3405\dot{W}_{\text{Comp}})^{0.62} \quad (3)$$

$$C_{\text{Pump}}^E = 10^{3.3892+0.0536\log_{10}\dot{W}_{\text{Pump}}+0.1538(\log_{10}\dot{W}_{\text{Pump}})^2} \quad (4)$$

$$C_{\text{HX}}^E = \left(\frac{Q_{\text{HX}}}{\Delta T_m}\right) \frac{C_{\text{PUV}}}{BV} \quad (5)$$

$$C_{\text{MSHE}}^E = 1.15 \left(\frac{Q_{\text{MSHE}}}{\Delta T_m}\right) \frac{C_{\text{PUV}}}{BV} \quad (6)$$

$$C_{\text{CW}}^E = \left(\frac{Q_{\text{CW}}}{\Delta T_m}\right) CV \quad (7)$$

The total installed equipment cost within the adopted LAES economic

Figure 4: Equipment cost breakdown, normalised per cubic metre of LH₂ storage capacity (£ per m³, on the 1000 m³ reservoir basis), showing the distribution between rotating and static equipment and the cost contribution of individual components.

The resulting equipment cost breakdown is shown in Figure 4, which distinguishes between rotating and static equipment and identifies the contribution of each individual component. The total installed equipment cost within the adopted LAES economic boundary is £701.6k, of which £606.3k (86.4%) corresponds to rotating equipment and £95.3k (13.6%) to static equipment. As Figure 4 indicates, the cost is dominated by the four-stage compression train, with a combined cost of £558.0k for C1, C2, C3 and C4, followed by the cold-box heat exchanger HEX101 at £68.7k. The four air expanders, K-101 to K-104, together account for £28.4k. The cost analysis also indicates that the low minimum temperature difference

imposed in the air intercoolers results in a relatively large required heat-transfer area, which increases the associated capital cost. In the present case, the four intercoolers together contribute £10.5k, suggesting that seawater-based intercooling may provide a more cost-effective solution for this section of the process. The cryogenic pump P-100 and the 30 m³ liquid-air storage tank contribute £19.5k and £11.3k, respectively.

4.2 Economic cost

The techno-economic assessment was performed using annualised capital cost, annual operating cost, annual storage value, and net present value as the main economic indicators. The annualised capital cost was calculated using Equation (8), where the total present capital cost C_c is converted into an equivalent yearly charge through the capital recovery factor based on the discount rate i and project life t .

$$CAC = C_c \left(\frac{i(1+i)^t}{(1+i)^t - 1} \right) \quad (8)$$

The total present capital cost itself was estimated from equation (9), which combines the purchase cost of each item of equipment with the corresponding bare-module factor and CEPCI correction to account for installation and cost-index escalation. In this expression, the summation over j covers the different equipment types, while the summation over k allows for equipment replacement over the project life when applicable.

$$C_c = 1.18 \sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^h \left[MF_j CR_j \frac{CEPCI_{2023}}{CEPCI_{Base,j}} \frac{1}{(1+i)^{k_j}(k_j-1)} \right] \quad (9)$$

The annual operating cost was then obtained from Eq. (10) as the sum of annual maintenance, taken as 2% of capital cost, and the annual electricity cost associated with off-peak charging.

$$AOC = 0.02C_c + P_{charge} h_{off-peak} C_{off-peak} \quad (10)$$

For the present system, the annual storage value was evaluated using equation (11). In contrast to a conventional sales-based formulation, ASV was defined here as the sum of two contributions: the annual value of electricity recovered during peak-time discharge and the annual value of hydrogen delivered as a byproduct stream.

$$ASV = P_{discharge} h_{peak} C_{peak} + \dot{m}_{H_2} h_{op} C_{H_2} \quad (11)$$

Finally, the overall economic viability was assessed through the net present value given by equation (12), where the discounted annual net cash flow is summed over 25 years, consistent with the assumed project lifetime adopted in this work. In this equation, the annual net cash flow includes the difference between ASV, AOC, and annual depreciation D , adjusted by the tax factor Φ , while the discount factor $(1+r)^y$ accounts for the time value of money in year y .

$$NPV = -C_c + \sum_{y=1}^{25} \frac{(ASV - AOC - D)(1-\Phi) + D}{(1+r)^y} \quad (12)$$

The resulting annualised techno-economic indicators are summarised in Table 2. Under the adopted economic boundary and the present assumptions for hydrogen and electricity valuation, the proposed system yields a positive net present value. The annual system value is dominated by the hydrogen byproduct stream, which contributes 98.8% of ASV, reflecting the benefit of recovering boil-off gas as a usable gaseous-hydrogen stream. In comparison, the direct contribution from LAES electricity arbitrage between off-peak and peak tariffs is modest, at about £3.2 k/yr. These results indicate that

the economic attractiveness of the integrated concept is governed mainly by hydrogen recovery, while the LAES subsystem provides a secondary but beneficial contribution through electricity storage and cold-energy utilisation.

Table 2. Annualised techno-economic indicators (3.6 kg/h LH₂ BOG basis).

Indicator	Value
Annualised capital cost (CAC)	£60.2 k/yr
Annual operating cost (AOC)	£20.8 k/yr
Annual system value (ASV)	£276.7 k/yr
H ₂ off-take revenue	£273.6 k/yr
peak-tariff electricity revenue	£3.2 k/yr
Net present value (25 yr, 7 %)	£1,610 k

To express the benefit of the cold-recovery loop in a normalised form, the annual LAES electricity output was related to the annual BOG flow processed through the cold-recovery loop. With $h_{op} = 8,000$ h/yr, the integrated system processes 28,800 kg/yr of BOG and dispatches 8,300 kWh/yr of electricity, corresponding to 0.288 kWh of dispatchable electricity per kilogram of BOG utilised in the cold-recovery loop. Using the UK time-weighted average electricity price the equivalent electricity value of this LAES-only contribution is £0.087 per kilogram of BOG processed. This value represents the economic contribution of cold-energy harvesting alone.

In addition to this electricity-storage contribution, the same BOG leaves the cold box as a warmed gaseous-hydrogen stream and, under the adopted vented-BOG baseline assumption, is assigned a value of £9.50/kg as a recoverable hydrogen byproduct. On this basis, the combined annual system value associated with each kilogram of BOG processed is about £9.59/kg, of which the LAES-only contribution remains small in comparison. This indicates that the dominant economic value of the integrated concept arises from hydrogen recovery, while the electricity-storage contribution provides an additional but secondary benefit.

Dominant Expressing the results on a storage-volume basis allows the integration to be scaled for any LH₂ inventory. Each cubic metre of stored LH₂ contains 70.953 kg of liquid hydrogen and, for the present design basis of 3.6 kg/h BOG from a 1000 m³ LH₂ reservoir, corresponds to a boil-off rate of 3.6×10^{-3} kg/h per m³ of LH₂. This is equivalent to 0.086 kg/day, or 28.8 kg/yr per m³ of LH₂, over 8000 operating hours per year, and corresponds to an effective BOG rate of about 0.12%/day for the 1000 m³ reservoir basis. When this BOG is utilised in the cold-recovery loop, it enables the production of 0.0340 kg/h of cryogenic air, equivalent to 272.2 kg/yr of liquid air per m³ of LH₂ stored.

The stored exergy associated with the liquid-air stream is 48.8 kWh/yr per m³ as mentioned in Fig. 2. When this cryogenic air is discharged through the expansion train over 4000 peak hours per year, the system delivers 8.30 kWh/yr of electricity per m³ of LH₂ inventory. Valued at the UK average electricity price of £0.301/kWh, this corresponds to an equivalent electricity value of £2.50/yr per m³ of

LH₂, while valuation at UK the peak tariff of £0.390/kWh gives £3.24/yr per m³. The principal per-cubic-metre LH₂ recovery and storage metrics derived from the present analysis are summarised in Table 3. The difference between stored liquid-air exergy and discharged electricity reflects the irreversibilities of the discharge train, including the pump, heaters, and expanders, as well as the limited performance of small-scale expansion equipment. Nevertheless, even at the present discharge efficiency, the integration converts a stream that would otherwise represent a pure exergy loss into a measurable storage-related value, with a clearly defined per-m³ scaling rule that can be applied to any LH₂ depot or distribution hub.

Table 3. Per-cubic-metre LH₂ recovery and storage metrics (8,000 h/yr operation, 4,000 h/yr discharge).

Quantity per m ³ of LH ₂ stored	Value
LH ₂ inventory	70.953 kg
BOG retrieved (cold-recovered)	28.80 kg/yr
Liquid air produced	272.2 kg/yr
Stored exergy in liquid air	48.8 kWh/yr
Electricity dispatched at discharge	8.30 kWh/yr
Equivalent energy cost at $C_{avg} = £0.301/kWh$	£2.50/yr
Equivalent value at UK peak tariff (£0.390/kWh)	£3.24/yr

5 Conclusion

This paper investigated the integration of LH₂ BOG cold recovery with a small-scale LAES system through a unified 3E assessment. The proposed configuration uses the unavoidable cryogenic exergy of LH₂ BOG as an external cold source for air liquefaction, while the warmed hydrogen stream remains available for subsequent chemical-exergy utilisation. The process was modelled in Aspen HYSYS using the REFPROP INST property dataset, and the compression stages were optimised in MATLAB to improve air-liquefaction performance. The results show that the integrated system achieves a liquefaction fraction of 90%, a charging specific energy consumption of 0.23 kWh/kg_{LAir}, and a figure of merit of 77.2%. The exergy analysis confirms that the LH₂ BOG stream supplies 5.6 kW of cryogenic exergy to the charging section, of which approximately 2.4 kW is usefully

transferred to the air side through the cold box. The largest exergy destruction occurs in the cold box and in the discharge-side heaters and expanders, indicating that future optimisation should focus on improved cold-box design, reduced heat-transfer irreversibility, and higher-efficiency small-scale expansion equipment.

The economic results indicate that the total installed equipment cost within the adopted LAES boundary is £701.6k, dominated by the four-stage air compression train. Under the selected assumptions, the system achieves a positive net present value of £1.61 million over 25 years at a 7% discount rate. The annual system value is governed mainly by recovery of the hydrogen byproduct stream, while electricity arbitrage from the LAES subsystem provides a smaller but still beneficial contribution. On a storage-volume basis, each cubic metre of LH₂ inventory enables the recovery of 28.8 kg/yr of BOG and the production of 272.2 kg/yr of liquid air, storing 48.8 kWh/yr of liquid-air exergy, of which 8.30 kWh/yr is dispatched as electricity during discharge; the difference reflects the irreversibility of the small-scale discharge train. The proposed concept demonstrates that LH₂ BOG can be converted from an unavoidable storage loss into a useful cryogenic and material resource. The results provide an initial design basis for LH₂ terminals with embedded cold-energy recovery, although further work is required on detailed cold-box design, pressure-drop assessment, manufacturability and capital-cost refinement.

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